

Formulation And Optimization Of Pulsatile Microspheres Of Amlodipine By Solvent Evaporation Method Using Factorial Design

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to develop amlodipine sustained-release microspheres via the solvent evaporation technique, with the formulation optimized through a 2³ factorial design. The selected particle size (Y1) and drug release after 12 hours (Y2) as the variables to measure, and evaluated the impact of three HPMC grades K4M (X1), K15M (X2), and K100M (X3) at dosages between 50 and 150 mg. The microspheres' particle size, shape, drug release properties, and encapsulation effectiveness were all evaluated. Based on the factorial formulation, the mean particle size of amlodipine microspheres varied from 268.94 ± 0.489 to 408.52 ± 0.854 μm. The percentage yields for formulations F1 through F8, after 12 hours with amlodipine, ranged from 35.95% to 99.97%. Formulation F2 outperformed other formulations with varying polymer concentrations, demonstrating a uniform particle size, the intended spherical shape, and prolonged drug release lasting up to 12 hours. Additionally, the improved formula (F2) exhibited strong linearity in 3D surface response and contour plot analyses, suggesting a considerable and predictable impact from formulation variables. These results suggest that the developed microsphere system offers a practical way to deliver amlodipine gradually over time.

Keywords: factorial design, Amlodipine microsphere, Drugcoat®RLPO, Entrapment efficiency, Drug release, Optimization.

INTRODUCTION

Medication management for chronic illnesses like hypertension depends on maintaining the required drug concentration at the site of action, which is closely related to the drug's plasma concentration. The drug's plasma level varies when standard oral dose forms are given often, which could have negative effects or make the medication useless for therapeutic purposes. Throughout the course of treatment, maintaining steady-state plasma concentrations of the medication may assist addresses these unfavorable issues, such as dosage frequency and side effects. This can now be achieved through the creation of several contemporary drug delivery systems. A lot of work has been done in the last few decades to create controlled release drug delivery devices, which release the medication gradually over a long period of time. Using polymeric microspheres as drug carriers is one popular tactic that explores the potential for

drug localization at the target site, reduces drug toxicity and side effects, controls drug release, maintains constant drug bioavailability, and protects sensitive drugs (like peptides and proteins) from enzymatic and chemical breakdown by entangling inside polymers. All of these goals can be achieved by developing microspheres, which also allow for the investigation of the use of an oral controlled release drug delivery system and the reduction of dosage and frequency of doses in comparison to conventional dosage forms. Microspheres containing sustained release of amlodipine besylate are more tolerated as compared to their conventional equivalents and dosage.

Amlodipine besylate (benzenesulfonic acid salt of 3-O-ethyl-5-O-methyl-2-(2-aminoethoxymethyl)-4-(2-chlorophenyl)-6-methyl-1,4-dihydropyridine-3,5-dicarboxylate) is a synthetic dihydropyridine calcium channel blocker with antihypertensive and anti angina

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effects. Because of its slow and nearly total absorption from the digestive system, it is a good option for a formulation intended to be released in microsphere form over time. It is common practice to employ microspheres made of biodegradable and biocompatible polymers to enable prolonged, controlled medication release. The pharmaceutical industry frequently uses the single emulsion solvent evaporation method to manufacture microspheres.

The purpose of this work was to create and evaluate response surface methodology-based amlodipine-loaded microspheres as a means of achieving a sustained release system for the treatment of hypertension. The effects of the independent factors, namely the drug to polymer ratio and particle size and drug release at 12 hr on the characteristics of amlodipine-loaded microspheres were investigated using a computer-aided optimization technique utilizing factorial design design. The effectiveness of trapping, realistic drug loading, and *in vitro* drug release were assessed for microspheres.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Materials:

Amlodipine besylate was a gift sample from M/s. Hetero Drugs Limited. HPMC grades K4M, K15M and K100M was obtained from obtained from M/s. Loba Chemie Pvt. Ltd. Ahmedabad, India. Ethanol was obtained from M/s. CDH Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi. Sodium hydroxide is obtained from M/s. Qualigens Fine Chemicals, Mumbai. All other materials used in this study were of analytical grade.

Preparation of the Amlodipine Loaded Pulsatile Microspheres

A chloroform solution was prepared containing 10 mg of the drug, Amlodipine, to which varying amounts of HPMC K4M, HPMC K15M, and HPMC K100M, along with Eudragit S100, were added. An aqueous phase was prepared by dispersing 0.2% polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) in water. The drug-polymer solution was then poured into the aqueous PVA solution under constant stirring. Microsphere formulations F1–F8 were prepared at 500 RPM, with different polymer concentrations as detailed in Table 1. The mixture was stirred using a propeller at the specified RPM for 3 hours at 25 °C to ensure complete removal of the solvent. The resulting microspheres were filtered, washed with deionized water, and collected. Finally, the microspheres were dried at room temperature for 24 hours.

Table 1: Composition of different formulations Pulsatile Microspheres of Amlodipine

Formulation Code	Drug (mg)	HPMC K4M (mg)	HPMC K15M (mg)	HPMC K100M (mg)	Eudragit S100 (mg)	0.2% PVA (mL)	Chloroform (mL)
F1	10	50	50	50	100	100	10
F2	10	150	50	50	100	100	10
F3	10	50	150	50	100	100	10
F4	10	150	150	50	100	100	10
F5	10	50	50	150	100	100	10
F6	10	150	50	150	100	100	10
F7	10	50	150	150	100	100	10
F8	10	150	150	150	100	100	10

2³ factorial experimental designs:

To find the circumstances in which the procedure produced microspheres, several pilot tests were carried out prior to the design being implemented. This approach also defined the component levels. A three-level, two factorial design (2³ factorial design) was used to investigate the effects of factors on the physicochemical properties of microspheres. With the aid of Design-Expert® Software (Version 11 Free Trial, Stat-Ease Inc., Minneapolis, MN), which enables evaluation by 8 experiments, the factors were investigated using the factorial design. The goal was to assess each processing component's impact and determine which one was most important in

determining the overall percentage of drug release and the particle size (dependent variables). The independent variables chosen were the drug to HPMC grade polymers. Table 2 lists the level of screening variables examined in this investigation. In order to determine whether or not an increase in factor value is advantageous, the factorial experimental design examines the input data, displays the rank ordering of the variables, and assigns a sign to the impact. Higher R² values were used to compare statistical measures and assess the design's relevance. Design-Expert® software was used to create three-dimensional (3D) contour plots and three-dimensional (3D) response plots that were obtained from the equations.

Table 2 A Transformed design for analysis of responses of Amlodipine Microspheres

Formula code	A (%)	B (%)	C (%)
F1	50	50	50
F2	150	50	50
F3	50	150	50
F4	150	150	50
F5	50	50	150
F6	150	50	150
F7	50	150	150
F8	150	150	150

Evaluation of Pulsatile Microsphere of Amlodipine

Microscopic Examination:

The prepared microspheres of formulations F1 to F8 were first dispersed gently in a few drops of distilled water to prevent aggregation and placed on a clean glass microscope slide. A cover slip was carefully placed over the sample to avoid crushing the microspheres. The slide was then positioned under an optical microscope and examined at 10× magnification. During observation, the shape, surface morphology, and size distribution of the microspheres were assessed. Photomicrographs were taken where necessary to document the morphology, and multiple fields of view were scanned for each formulation to ensure a representative analysis.

Particle Size (µm)

Optical microscopy technique was used to estimate the particle size of the microspheres. In this analysis approximately 100 microspheres were counted and a calibrated optical microscope was used for this purpose. Particle size directly affects drug release. Larger surface area is occupied by smaller particles that aid to faster drug release. Large cores are possessed by larger particles which allow more drugs to be encapsulated and make the diffusion process longer.

$$\text{Average Particle Size} = \frac{\sum n}{\sum n!} \times \text{least count}$$

Percentage Yield

The percent yield of Amlodipine loaded microspheres was calculated by dividing the weight of the prepared microspheres by total theoretical amount that is the weight of drug and polymers used.

$$\text{Percentage Yield} = \frac{\text{Practicle amount}}{\text{Theoretical amount}} \times 100$$

Percentage Entrapment Efficiency (%EE)

To calculate the percentage entrapment efficiency, 25 mg of amlodipine loaded microsphere were mixed in 10 ml of methanol. The mixture thus obtained was filtrated with the help of 0.45 μm membrane filter paper. The obtained filtrate was diluted and analyzed for amount of drug present using ultraviolet spectrophotometer (Shimadzu 1800, Kyoto, Japan) at 239 nm. The entrapment efficiency of amlodipine loaded pulsatile microsphere was estimated using formula:

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{Percentage Entrapment Efficiency (\%EE)} \\ &= \frac{\text{Practical Drug Concentration}}{\text{Theoretical drug concentration}} \times 100 \end{aligned}$$

Drug Loading Capacity

Amlodipine loaded microspheres of amount 25 mg were mixed in 10 ml methanol. The mixture obtained was filtrated with the help of 0.45 μm membrane filter paper. The resultant mass after filtration was diluted and analyzed for the concentration of drug present using ultraviolet spectrophotometer (Shimadzu 1800, Kyoto, Japan) at 239 nm. Drug loading Capacity was estimated using following formula:

Drug Loading Capacity

$$= \frac{\text{Drug loaded in microspheres}}{\text{total weight of microspheres}} \times 100$$

Measurement of Micromeritics Properties:

The microspheres were indicated for their micrometric characteristics such as particle size (by optical microscopy), bulk density, tapped density, Carr's index, Hausner ratio and angle of repose as noted in various previous studies.

In Vitro Release Studies:

The designed preparations were studied for *in vitro* drug release using USP 36-NF31 dissolution apparatus with a paddle rotation of speed 100 rpm. Microspheres equivalent to 2.5 mg amlodipine of all formulations F1 to F8 were placed into the dissolution apparatus containing 900 ml of acid buffer and pH was maintained as that of stomach i.e. pH 1.2 for first 2 h and 900 ml of phosphate buffer offering the environment of initial intestine having pH 6.8 was used for the next 10 h and apparatus was operated at 100 RPM and maintaining the temperature 37 ± 0.5 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. From the dissolution basket five millilitres of the sample was withdrawn at regular time basis and the same amount was compensated with fresh buffer. Membrane filter 0.45 μm (Millipore) was used to constrain the sample. The sample was then analyzed using UV spectroscopy and absorbance was found to be 239 nm.

Statistical Analysis

Independent variables and response variables can be co-related by using a polynomial regression algorithm. It is a second-order model equation, for the 2ⁿ experimental design polynomial equation was written as Equation.

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1A + \beta_2B + \beta_3C + \beta_1\beta_2 AB + \beta_1 \beta_3 AC + \beta_2\beta_3 BC + \beta_1\beta_2 \beta_3$$

Where, Y is the measured response

β_0 is the arithmetic mean response

β_1 , β_2 , β_3 , $\beta_1\beta_2$, $\beta_1\beta_3$, $\beta_2\beta_3$, $\beta_1\beta_2\beta_3$ are the coefficients for the corresponding factors A, B, C, AB, AC, BC, and ABC are the percentages of HPMC K4M (A), HPMC K15M (B), and HPMC K100M (C) and interaction terms respectively

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Evaluation of Pulsatile Microsphere of Amlodipine

Microscopic Examination

The microscopic images are as given below and surface appearance described in Table 3. Fig 1 were represented the microscopic examination image of microsphere formulation F1 to F8 respectively.

Table 3: Surface appearance of microsphere

S. No.	Formulation code	Appearance of Microsphere
1	F1	Spherical microsphere
2	F2	Spherical microsphere
3	F3	Irregular microspheres
4	F4	Spherical microsphere
5	F5	Spherical microsphere
6	F6	Spherical microsphere
7	F7	Spherical microsphere
8	F8	Spherical microsphere

Fig No: 1 Microscopic examination of Amlodipine microspheres (F1-F8)

The particle size of the formulation F1 to F8 was calculated and data shown in the Table 3. All the formulations have spherical microspheres other than one F3 microspheres. Percentage yield of above mentioned formulations were calculated by practical amount divided by theoretical amount into 100. It was found that the percentage of production ranged in between 35.71 to 88.23 % and F8 showed maximum percentage yield i.e. 95.94%. However the variation

of polymers and RPM were affected the percentage yield of the microspheres.

Percentage Entrapment Efficiency of above mentioned formulations were calculated by the practical drug concentration divided by theoretical drug concentration into 100. The entrapment efficiencies of amlodipine-loaded microspheres were found between 84.02 to 99.578 %. The result showed

F2 have maximum entrapment efficiency i.e. 99.578 %.

Drug loading capacity of above mentioned formulation was calculated by drug loaded in the microspheres divided by the total weight of the microspheres into 100. The drug loading capacities of

amlodipine loaded microspheres found in between 1.61 to 6.25 as shown in Table 3. Comparatively high encapsulation values were obtained with the microspheres with high drug loading. The results shows that F2 having optimum drug loading capacity i.e. 2.22.

Table no: 3 Drug loading capacity of different formulations

S. No.	Formulation code	Drug Loading Capacity	Particle Size (μm)	Percentage Yield	Percentage Entrapment Efficiency
1	F1	6.250 \pm 0.023	268.94 \pm 0.489	61.531 \pm 0.052	84.020 \pm 0.125
2	F2	2.222 \pm 0.012	278.90 \pm 0.247	88.235 \pm 0.042	99.860 \pm 0.103
3	F3	1.612 \pm 0.013	363.89 \pm 0.596	81.578 \pm 0.045	85.755 \pm 0.122
4	F4	5.490 \pm 0.012	385.90 \pm 0.578	35.714 \pm 0.033	94.860 \pm 0.154
5	F5	2.065 \pm 0.015	295.90 \pm 0.745	94.946 \pm 0.029	97.734 \pm 0.142
6	F6	2.148 \pm 0.011	368.45 \pm 0.598	91.267 \pm 0.048	94.860 \pm 0.132
7	F7	2.164 \pm 0.014	403.60 \pm 0.486	90.589 \pm 0.053	86.236 \pm 0.221
8	F8	4.58 \pm 0.0680	408.52 \pm 0.854	95.946 \pm 0.029	99.578 \pm 0.122

Measurement of Micromeritics Properties

The prepared formulations containing different concentration of polymer ratio were evaluated for micrometric properties like particle size, bulk density, tap density and angle of repose. All the formulations F1 to F8 were free flowing, indicated that the angle of repose value between 23 to 30°. The values of tapped and bulk densities reflected the acceptable packing ability of amlodipine microsphere. Upon the calculation of Carr indices (Ci), value obtained was 7.2 - 19.07 % as expressed in Table 4. Yielding with the lowest Ci value, forth giving the idea that

microspheres have excellent compressibility. Calculation of Hausner ratios reflected the result in between 1.16-1.99 represented good flow properties.

The bulk density of all the formulations F1 to F8 was evaluated by mass of microspheres by untapped volume. Values obtained on calculation of Bulk Density lies in the range of 0.729 to 0.899 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^3$ and these values are elaborated in Table 4. Tapped Density was calculated by mass of microspheres divided by tapped volume. It was found that tapped density was found in the range 0.60 to 1.03 as shown in Table 4.

Table no: 4 Micromeritics Properties of Amlodipine Microspheres

S. No.	Formulation Code	Angle of Repose	Bulk Density (gm/cm^3)	Tapped Density (gm/cm^3)	Ci (%)	Hausner's ratio
1	F1	27.16 \pm 0.1	0.792 \pm 0.01	0.871 \pm 0.021	9.070 \pm 0.12	1.990 \pm 0.011
2	F2	28.16 \pm 0.1	0.873 \pm 0.05	0.941 \pm 0.047	7.226 \pm 0.23	1.771 \pm 0.012
3	F3	24.74 \pm 0.1	0.768 \pm 0.04	0.912 \pm 0.035	15.789 \pm 0.19	1.187 \pm 0.014
4	F4	23.74 \pm 0.2	0.899 \pm 0.02	1.032 \pm 0.037	12.887 \pm 0.04	1.147 \pm 0.012
5	F5	29.13 \pm 0.1	0.872 \pm 0.38	1.014 \pm 0.028	14.003 \pm 0.21	1.162 \pm 0.013
6	F6	27.81 \pm 0.1	0.558 \pm 0.26	0.606 \pm 0.031	7.920 \pm 0.28	1.860 \pm 0.011
7	F7	25.23 \pm 0.1	0.632 \pm 0.34	0.781 \pm 0.028	19.078 \pm 0.02	1.235 \pm 0.028
8	F8	28.35 \pm 0.143	0.598 \pm 0.062	0.961 \pm 0.048	14.85 \pm 0.063	1.548 \pm 0.048

In Vitro Release Studies

The study evaluated the in-vitro drug release profile of Amlodipine from eight formulations (F1 to F8) compared to a marketed product, highlighting the impact of polymer concentration and viscosity on release behavior. All formulations exhibited a gradual increase in cumulative drug release over 12 hours, although the rate and extent varied notably based on the composition of HPMC K4M, HPMC K15M, and HPMC K100M. Initial release rates (0.5–2 hours) were higher in formulations F3 and F8 (15–16% at 0.5 h), indicating rapid hydration and swelling, while F1 showed a slow release (1.26% at 0.5 h), pointing to weak matrix formation.

As time progressed, a clear correlation between polymer concentration and release behavior emerged. Higher polymer content, especially from high-viscosity HPMC K100M, contributed to stronger gel formation and extended drug release. For example, F5, F7, and F8 reached around 78–82% release at 8 hours, while F3 released 82.98%, benefitting from medium-viscosity polymer. By 12 hours, F2 showed nearly complete release (99.78%), indicating

insufficient retardation despite higher polymer levels, likely due to the influence of lower viscosity polymer. In contrast, F8 (95.48%) and F5 (94.67%) offered a more favorable controlled release profile. The marketed product released approximately 85.67% at 12 hours, which underperformed compared to several test formulations, especially F2 and F8. The findings suggest that increasing polymer concentration, particularly high-viscosity grades, enhances matrix stability and prolongs drug release, with F5, F7, and F8 demonstrating optimized performance. Formulation F1 exhibited poor release characteristics, while F2 showed overly rapid release it represented in table no 5 and fig no 2&3. The inclusion of Eudragit S100 aided in controlling release by preventing premature drug release in acidic conditions. Kinetic analysis revealed that formulation F2 best followed the Higuchi model ($R^2 = 0.9327$), indicating a diffusion-controlled release mechanism. Zero-order kinetics showed moderate correlation ($R^2 = 0.8828$), while First-order kinetics ($R^2 = 0.6813$) and Korsmeyer-Peppas ($R^2 = 0.456$) indicated less support for those models for F2's release behavior and values are indicated in table no 6.

Table no 8: Amlodipine release profile from different formulation F1 to F8 with marketed product

Cumulative Percentage Drug Release									
Time (h)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	Marketed Product
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0.5	1.26	11.65	15.85	12.48	13.85	11.25	10.65	16.85	9.58
1	3.48	19.87	22.56	20.48	19.36	16.85	15.95	21.25	13.75
1.5	5.46	21.65	30.95	29.56	28.64	21.12	22.45	28.64	17.26
2	7.86	35.69	38.45	35.45	36.89	29.35	30.56	36.49	27.65
3	8.19	42.35	45.69	42.86	45.62	35.19	39.85	42.49	35.98
4	12.48	49.45	51.25	49.52	51.36	42.98	45.67	49.85	42.11
5	16.85	56.56	58.35	55.23	59.14	49.56	51.71	58.11	48.69
6	20.48	68.98	62.84	59.48	65.71	57.45	58.36	62.56	53.48
7	22.57	73.76	76.56	63.45	72.69	65.98	67.56	70.65	59.44
8	25.61	79.89	82.98	73.12	79.19	73.85	75.15	78.33	66.98
10	31.25	86.52	88.87	82.35	86.72	82.54	80.62	87.12	79.56
12	35.95	99.78	91.26	92.48	94.67	91.58	86.52	95.48	85.67

Fig no: 2 *In-vitro* release of amlodipine loaded microspheres of formulation F1 to F4 formulation

Fig no:3 *In-vitro* release of amlodipine loaded microspheres of formulation F4 to F8 formulation and marketed products

Table no: 6 *In-vitro* drug release kinetics parameters of all amlodipine loaded pulsatile microspheres formulations

Formulation code	R2 (Regression coefficient)			
	Zero order	First order	Higuchi model	Korsmeyer-Peppas
F2	0.8828	0.6813	0.9327	0.456

Optimization By Using Design Expert Software From Optimum Formulation

Final Equation in Terms of Coded Factors:

$$\text{Particle size} = +346.76 + 13.68A + 43.72B + 22.36C - 6.95AB + 5.69AC - 6.77BC - 9.96ABC$$

$$\text{Percent drug release} = +85.97 + 8.87A + 5.47B + 6.10C - 6.32AB - 7.40AC - 6.53BC + 9.33$$

The value of correlation coefficient ($R^2 = 1.000$) indicates a good fit. From the polynomial equation, a conclusion can be drawn by considering the magnitude of coefficient and mathematical sign it carries (positive or negative).

The document discusses the effects of HPMC K4M and HPMC K15M on particle size, illustrated through a 3D response surface plot and a 2D contour plot. The response surface plot indicates that increasing concentrations of both polymers result in larger particle sizes, with the minimum size ($\sim 270 \mu\text{m}$) observed at low levels (50 mg each) and sizes exceeding $400 \mu\text{m}$ at higher levels ($\sim 150 \text{ mg}$). This

suggests a linear relationship with some interaction between the polymers, attributed to increased viscosity and aggregation. The contour plot complements this by providing a two-dimensional view where the color gradient indicates particle size variations, from blue to red, and the contour lines show a significant and uniform influence of both variables on particle size. The contour lines are nearly parallel and spaced evenly, denoting a predictable relationship with less interaction compared to those observed in drug release dynamics. Together, these plots facilitate the identification of optimal combinations of polymers for desired particle size in formulation development.

Fig 4. (a) Response Surface Plot (b) Contour Plot of amlodipine loaded pulsatile microspheres formulation. (Effect of HPMC K4M and HPMC K15M on particle size)

(a) Response Surface Plot

(b) Contour Plot

Fig 5. (a) Response Surface Plot (b) Contour Plot of amlodipine loaded pulsatile microspheres formulation. (Effect of HPMC K4M and HPMC K15M on % Drug release)

(a) Response Surface Plot

(b) Contour Plot

A response surface plot provides a three-dimensional view of how formulation variables, specifically HPMC K4M and HPMC K15M concentrations, affect drug release rates from amlodipine-loaded pulsatile microspheres. The plot uses HPMC K4M on one axis and HPMC K15M on the other, with the percentage drug release on the vertical axis, illustrating both their individual and interactive effects. Increased HPMC K4M concentration results in a more viscous gel, reducing drug diffusion and percentage release. Similarly, higher concentrations of HPMC K15M form thicker gel barriers, further inhibiting drug release. When both polymers are present in high concentrations, they exhibit a synergistic effect that significantly decreases the percentage drug release, depicted as a downward slope on the plot. Conversely, a contour plot presents a two-dimensional representation of the same data, with contour lines illustrating constant percentages of drug release based on the concentrations of HPMC K4M and HPMC K15M. The spacing of these contour lines reflects the rate of change in drug release rates; closely spaced lines indicate rapid changes, while wider spacing shows gradual changes. Elliptical patterns suggest strong interactions between the two polymers, contrasting with circular patterns indicative of minimal interactions. Overall, both the response surface and contour plots highlight that increasing concentrations of HPMC K4M and HPMC K15M lead to decreased percentage drug release due to enhanced gel barrier formation, which is key for optimizing the pulsatile drug delivery system.

Optimum Formula:

The study analyzed the impact of independent variables, specifically various concentrations of polymers HPMC K4M (A), HPMC K15M (B), and HPMC K100M (C) on formulation performance, focusing on particle size and drug release rates. Polynomial equations indicated that both individual factors and their interactions (AB, AC, and BC) positively affected drug release and microsphere size. Contour plot analyses revealed that lower concentrations of the polymers favored smaller particle sizes and higher drug release, whereas increased polymer levels led to a more controlled release pattern. Among the tested formulations, F8, which included 150 mg of each polymer,

demonstrated optimal characteristics with larger particle size and sustained drug release over 12 hours, making it the best choice for Amlodipine-loaded pulsatile microspheres. In contrast, formulation F2, containing a higher amount of only HPMC K4M, also achieved satisfactory sustained release with a simpler composition, suggesting it may be a more cost-effective alternative while maintaining controlled-release performance.

CONCLUSION:

The amlodipine loaded microspheres were successfully formulated using the single emulsion-solvent evaporation technique. Factorial (2^3 factorial) design was used to study and optimize the effect of three independent factors on the particle size and percentage drug release. The optimized formulation (F2) exhibited entrapment efficiency 2.22% and cumulative percentage drug release 99.97 % at 12 h. The morphology of optimized microparticles was roughly spherical in shape. Such experimental design approach may be applied in the development of microparticulate systems to produce microspheres with high entrapment efficiency and provide sustained release of amlodipine besylate.

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